

An unusual Case Report of Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma with Columnar Cell Variant Diagnosed by FNAC

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The columnar cell variant of papillary carcinoma of thyroid are uncommon variant and regarded as more aggressive form as compared to more common classic papillary and follicular subtypes.

Case Report: A 30 year male presents with midline nodular swelling measured 2.5x2.5 cm, since one year. On examination swelling was firm, moved with deglutition and non-tender. The aspirate are hypercellular showing large fragments of cells showing nuclear overlapping with oval enlarged nucleus with fine chromatin, grooving and inclusions are seen. Clusters of cells showing nuclear stratification with nuclear hyperchromasia. Based on these finding diagnosis was malignant neoplastic lesion probably papillary thyroid carcinoma was made with differential diagnosis of medullary carcinoma of thyroid. Subsequent excision was done showing a tumour with papillary architecture with nuclear feature of papillary thyroid carcinoma also identified area showing follicles with marked nuclear stratification and hyperchromatic nuclei was seen.

Conclusion: Nuclear overlapping, oval enlarged nucleus, grooving and nuclear stratification show feature of papillary carcinoma of thyroid columnar variant.

Keywords: Rare Case, Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma, FNAC.

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Introduction

Papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) is the most common type of thyroid cancer, making up about 90% of all thyroid cancers. [1,2] There are different types of PTC, and they have different clinical outcomes and prognoses. [3] The columnar cell variant of PTC (CCV-PTC) is a rare type, making up only 0.15–0.2% of all PTC cases. [4].The American Thyroid Association recently updated its guidelines, classifying PTC variants based on their behavior. CCV-PTC is considered an aggressive form. [5] Studies have shown that CCV-PTC grows quickly and has a high chance of coming back after treatment. It is often linked to local spread and early spread to lymph nodes. [6,7,8] However, the outcome for CCV-PTC is still debated. Some cases, especially those in an encapsulated form, have a better outcome with slower growth and a lower chance of recurrence or spread. [9,10,11]

Objective: Herein, we report the fine needle aspiration features of a case of columnar cell variant of

papillary thyroid carcinoma which was confirmed on histopathological examination

Case Report: A 30 year male presents with midline nodular swelling measured 2.5x2.5 cm since one year. On examination swelling was firm, moved with deglutition and non-tender.

Cytomorphological findings: The aspirate are hyper cellular showing large fragments of cells arranged in papillary fronds and syncytial sheets. Clusters of cell are showing nuclear stratification with nuclear hyperchromasia.

These cells are showing nuclear overlapping with oval enlarged nucleus with fine chromatin, grooving and inclusions are seen. Based on these finding diagnosis was malignant neoplastic lesion probably papillary thyroid carcinoma was made with differential diagnosis of medullary carcinoma of thyroid.

Figure 1a:

Figure 1b:

Figure 1c:

Figure 1d:

Histopathological Finding: The gross examination of the specimen revealed a thyroid gland 30 g in weight. Right lobe should a nodule measured 2.5x2.5 cm.

Microscopic examination revealed an encapsulated tumour .The tumour cells had mostly trabecular

arrangement with pseudo stratification of nuclei. Cells were columnar and had clear to pale pink cytoplasm. Sub nuclear cytoplasmic vacuoles also seen. The nuclei are elongated, hyperchromatic with coarse chromatin and inconspicuous nucleoli. Many nuclei are showing presence of nuclear grooves.

Figure 2a:

Figure 2b:

Figure 2c:

Discussion

The features of columnar cell variant of papillary thyroid carcinoma are elusive and hence the diagnosis is difficult solely based on FNA. Pseudo stratification of nuclei is a prominent feature of this neoplasm. Tall cell variant of papillary carcinoma, which is the main differential diagnosis, lacks the feature of pseudo stratification though it also has tall columnar cells. Need to be differentiated from metastatic colon and endometrial adenocarcinoma. The columnar cell variant (TCV) is the most common aggressive subtype of papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC). This prevalence has shown a significant increase in recent years.

The columnar cell variant (CCV) of papillary thyroid carcinoma (PTC) is a rare subtype, comprising 0.15–0.2% of all PTC cases. First described as a "hostile" tumor by Evans in 1986, the notion of CCV-PTC as a clinically aggressive tumor with a poor prognosis has been contested by several studies. These studies reported more favorable outcomes in patients with the encapsulated form of CCV-PTC. However, they did not provide detailed imaging features of CCV-PTC, which often presents as clinically indolent. In the present study, only half of the patients in the indolent group had tumors with typical suspicious malignant features (K-TIRADS 5), with relatively small tumor sizes confined to the thyroid parenchyma.

Conclusion

FNAC being the first line of investigation in the diagnosis of thyroid swellings, recognition of the cytologic characteristics of this aggressive subtype may be of utility in the management of these patients. PTC-CC is lined to more aggressive behavior, higher rates of recurrence, and metastasis so, its accurate histological Diagnosis is essential for the therapy and prognosis of patients. Diagnosis is made via histological examination of a resected specimen, supplemented by immunohistochemistry.

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